

Article

Physiological Foundations of Endurance in Sports Tourism and The Effects of The External Environment on The Body

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Abstract: In Uzbekistan, there is a wide range of opportunities for sports tourism in desert, steppe and mountainous regions. The physiological basis of endurance in sports tourism and the great influence of the external environment on the body was analyzed. According to age and social characteristics, sports tourism is divided into children's tourism, youth tourism, adult tourism, family tourism, tourism for the disabled, etc.

Keywords: Sports Tourism, Endurance, Organism, External Environment, Children's Tourism, Youth Tourism, Adult Tourism, Family Tourism

1. Introduction

Sports tourism serves as a powerful tool for students to participate in various traditional sports holidays and share their impressions. The essence of sports tourism is reflected in the content of the joint activities of the student and the teacher. The concept of "endurance" is used in a very broad sense to describe a person's ability to perform one or another type of mental or physical muscular activity for a long time. The characteristics of endurance are relative: it applies only to a certain type of activity [1]. In other words, endurance is individual - it manifests itself in each person when performing a certain, specific type of activity [2].

Endurance of physical muscular work performed in sports tourism is divided into the following: 1. Static and dynamic endurance. 2. Local and global endurance. 3. Strength endurance. 4. Includes anaerobic and aerobic endurance. Sports that require endurance include all aerobic exercises of a cyclic nature, in particular, 1500 m running, cycling, skiing, 3000 m skating, 400 m swimming, etc [3]. Today, one of the most pressing problems in sports tourism is the study of the physiological foundations of endurance and the effects of the external environment on the body [4].

2. Materials and Method

In sports physiology, endurance is usually associated with the performance of sports exercises that require the participation of large muscle mass, approximately half or more of the total muscle mass of the body, and that last for 2-3 minutes or more. Observation, comparison, and experimental methods were used in the work.

3. Results

Sports touri is a type of sport aimed at improving a person through sports in overcoming natural obstacles. Sports skills in tourism consist in overcoming natural obstacles, using various tactics and methods. As in other official sports, sports tourism has an organized and professional refereeing, and its activities are regulated by relevant regulatory documents [5]. Many sports tourists also engage in relevant sports, such as track and multi-sport, mountaineering, mountain biking, skiing, swimming, and others. Sports tourists, including those who are trained as rescuers in natural environments, are a reserve. Sports tourism, primarily sports trips, are a team sport with strong traditions of mutual assistance and sports discipline, self-improvement, and mutual exchange of knowledge and experience [6]. In Uzbekistan, desert, steppe and mountainous regions have wide opportunities for sports tourism. The steppe zone covers areas with an altitude of 400-500 m above sea level and occupies 70% of the territory of Uzbekistan [7]. The Adyr region is located at altitudes from 400-500 m to 1000-1200 m above sea level, occupying the foothills. The climate of the Adyr differs slightly from the desert climate, but summers are hot and long [8]. Summers are not as hot as in the desert, with an annual rainfall of 300-450 mm. The vegetation cover is thicker than in the desert. The mountain zone covers areas with an altitude of 1000-1200 m to 2700-2800 m above sea level [9]. As you rise in altitude, the air temperature decreases and the amount of precipitation increases. Summers in the mountains are cooler and shorter than in the desert. Tokai - Tokai are found on the banks of such rivers of our republic as the Syrdarya, Amu Darya, Zarafshan, Chirchik, and Akhangaran. The widespread use of these natural ecosystems in sports tourism is of great importance [10]. Passion for sports tourism allows you to get acquainted with the culture and life of different countries and peoples, beautiful and often even unique corners of nature, interesting sights, enjoy communication and find reliable companions [11]. Participation in sports campaigns in the initial categories of difficulty and in distance competitions, as a rule, does not require large financial costs, but at the same time allows you to master the basic skills you need and enjoy participating in campaigns and competitions [12]. Mastering sports tourism as a comprehensive sport carried out in a complex natural and social environment requires multifaceted knowledge, skills, experience and good preparation from the athlete. In large cities, there are many sports tourism organizations and amateur tourist clubs [13]. Equipment in sports tourism depends on its type and includes special clothing.

4. Discussion

The main skills of a tourist include: providing first aid, organizing and conducting evacuation of victims, selecting and setting up camps and temporary stopping places, working with ropes and managing technical equipment crossings, insurance, etc., movement techniques and overcoming obstacles of other nature, organizing the order of movement in a group and other actions, etc. Additional skills include useful knowledge of the hiking zone or the relevant types and types of sports of general tourism, hunting and fishing skills, working with animals and various techniques, geography, and the environment [14]. The following types of sports tourism in Uzbekistan are distinguished: - hiking - movement in the tourist direction is carried out mainly on foot.

- Ski tourism - movement in the tourist direction is carried out mainly on skis.
- Mountain tourism - hiking in high mountains.
- Water tourism.
- Speleotourism - travel through underground cavities.
- Sailing tourism - travel on ships sailing in the water areas of large lakes.

- By means of transport - bicycle tourism, equestrian tourism and automobile tourism [15]. In Uzbekistan, according to age and social characteristics, sports tourism is divided into: children's tourism, youth tourism, adult tourism, family tourism, tourism for the disabled, etc.

5. Conclusion

In Uzbekistan, there is a wide range of opportunities for sports tourism in desert, steppe and mountainous regions. The physiological basis of endurance in sports tourism and the great influence of the external environment on the body was analyzed. According to age and social characteristics, sports tourism is divided into children's tourism, youth tourism, adult tourism, family tourism, tourism for the disabled, etc.

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